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Leadership Style And Organizational Service Delivery: A Study Of NYSC Anambra State 2018-2023

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the leadership style and organizational service delivery of NYSC Anambra State. The specific objectives of the study were to; examine the effect of authoritarian style of leadership on organizational service delivery of NYSC Anambra State; determine the effect of laissez a faire style of leadership on organizational service delivery of NYSC Anambra State; determine the effect of democratic style of leadership on organizational service delivery of NYSC Anambra State. Three research question and hypotheses are formulated in line with the objectives. The study is anchored on Traits and Behavioral Theory and adopted survey method of research. Data were generated through primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the NYSC staff of the selected local government area in Onitsha. The populations and sample size of the study was 173. One hundred and seventy-three (173) questionnaires were administered to the respondents but one hundred and thirty-five (135) were retrieved and it is based on 135 retrieved questionnaires that the analysis was carried out. The hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed, Authoritarian style of leadership has significant effect on organizational service delivery. Laissez a faire style of leadership has significant effect on organizational service delivery. Democratic style of leadership has no significant effect on organizational service delivery. The study recommends that; Leaders of business organization should adopt participative style of leadership to ensure success and growth of their business; Leaders should instill in their subordinates a sense of ownership, direction and belongingness to the organization.

Keywords: Authoritarian style, laissez a faire, leadership style, democratic style, service delivery

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is one of the factors that play a significant role in enhancement and retention of the interest and commitment of employees in organizations. Organizations, group, institutions developed and even the emerging economies of the world faces leadership problem. The success or failure of any organization depends on the leadership and its styles. Messick and Krammer (2014) argued that the degree to which the individual exhibits leadership traits depends not only on his characteristics and personal abilities but also in the characteristic of the situation and the environment in which he operate.

Leaders' authority can be great or limited and their legitimacy can rest on moral, rational, or practical foundations (Epley, 2015). Leadership is a dynamic process of influencing people which, in certain

organizational conditions, can have an effect on other members, with the aim of meeting the objectives of the group. Leadership is key as it is an integral element in the life of an individual or that of an organization. The history of mankind reveals that leadership is crucial in every human endeavour, from China with Chairman Mao TseTun who led the Cultural Revolution, to Lenin in Soviet Union who led the Soviet revolution to Nigeria where we have leaders of note like the late Chief Obafemi Awolowo. It is clear that leadership is an important factor in every human activity and in the realisation of human aims and objectives (Bass & Bass, 2018). There is no meaningful human endeavour that has been achieved that is not as a result of leadership. The quality of leadership of an organisation plays a significant role in its development for example in a pluralistic society like Nigeria, the art of governance is ought to be a serious affair. Although it has been found that many who are involved in leadership in Nigeria educational institutions are more concerned about their personal gains and careless about the people they ought to serve and lead (Peretomode, 2012 in Nakpodia, 2012).

Leadership is a major concern to organizations and that is the reason why it is the focus of several researchers for its significant role in determining the success of an organization. The leader has the responsibility to direct the effort of subordinates to achieve organisational goals and objectives. Leadership as a term is arguably one of the most observed and yet least understood phenomena on earth (Burns in Abbasialiya, 2017). In past years, scholars have proposed many different styles of leadership as there is no particular style that can be considered universal. Despite the numerous style of leadership, an effective leader inspires, motivates and directs activities to help achieve organisational goals. It is widely known that leadership plays an important role in all organisations. Hence the study examines the effect of leadership style on employee's performance

Statement of Problems

Goal attainment is one of the main purposes of modern organizations including educational institutions. There is a growing interest to determine which leadership style is capable of enhancing employee's morale in such a way that brewery firms can achieve its goals and objectives optimally. Issues of leadership styles in organizations in Nigeria have been raised in many instances, by trying to find out the causes of poor standard of brewery firms in Nigeria. It seem to be out of the mind of most leaders that leadership style in the office is an outstanding determinant of the worker's performance. More so, if workers who are also employees do not portray a good leadership style, it would also serve as a determinant on the company's performance. Issues like this are of utmost importance in a situation where employees seem to have lost the passion and commitment for their job. It is believed that some employees of the life brewery are better in maintaining discipline in their offices through the leadership styles. In life brewery, the leadership qualities of the chief executives become very important because a lot of power resides in the manager of a life brewery and the way this power is wielded determines how the community receives decisions and policies. At the Federal polytechnic, Ilaro leadership has always been an issue. One of the problems of leadership style on employee's performance is the inflexibility of the leadership styles by most leaders. Most leaders fail to adjust their style

The failure is a result of the lack of understanding the fact that no one particular style of leadership can fit into all conditions. Another of the problem of leadership style on worker's performance is the absence of an effective line of communication between the manager and their employees. Communication gaps that exist between leaders and their subordinates in most organisations are reasons why employee's performances are low. Leadership is said to be the backbone of any organisation. If the leadership style of any organisation is poor, it will tell on the overall performance of the organisation. With this understanding, most organisations are faced with the problems of how to investigate the leadership styles and organisational effectiveness. Knowing whether the relationship between leaders and subordinates affect organisational growth and even having broad knowledge of the leadership style adopted by the organisation can improve organisational effectiveness. It is on this ground that this paper aims to assess the extent leadership styles influences organizational service delivery: A study of NYSC Anambra State

Objectives of Study

The main purpose of the study is to investigate the effect of leadership style on organizational service delivery: A study of NYSC Anambra State

Based on this, the specific purpose are.

- i. To examine the effect of authoritarian style of leadership on organizational service delivery of NYSC Anambra State
- ii. To determine the effect of laissez a faire style of leadership on organizational service delivery of NYSC Anambra State
- iii. To determine the effect of democratic style of leadership on organizational service delivery of NYSC Anambra State

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were formulated for the purpose of this work.

H01: Authoritarian style of leadership has no significant effect on organizational service delivery of NYSC Anambra State

H0₂: Laissez a faire style of leadership has no significant effect on organizational service delivery of NYSC Anambra State

H0₃: Democratic style of leadership has no significant effect on organizational service delivery of NYSC Anambra State

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Review

Traits and Behavioral Theory

Thomas Carlyle first proposed the theory in the 1800. Trait leadership is defined as integrated patterns of personal characteristics that reflect a range of individual differences and foster consistent leader effectiveness across a variety of group and organizational situations (Ackerman & Humphreys, 1992).

The theory is developed from early leadership research which focused primarily on finding a group of heritable attributes that differentiate leaders from nonleaders. Leader effectiveness refers to the amount of influence a leader has on individual or group performance, followers' satisfaction, and overall effectiveness (Avolio, et al., 2003). Many scholars have argued that leadership is unique to only a select number of individuals, and that these individuals possess certain immutable traits that cannot be developed (Barrick, Mitchell & Stewart, 2003). Although this perspective has been criticized immensely over the past century, scholars still continue to study the effects of personality traits on leader effectiveness.

The trait perspective was one of the earliest theories of leadership in the 1940's which assumes that great leaders are born with distinguished personality traits that make them better suited for leadership and make them different from other people or their followers. Stogdill's (1948) survey of the leadership literature came up with the most comprehensive list of traits. Stogdill's observation that leadership situations vary significantly and place different demands on leaders, destroyed trait theory, leading to the emergence of situational and behavioral approaches. Behavioral theories of leadership state that it is the behavior of leaders that distinguishes them from their followers. It focuses on the actions of leaders rather than on mental qualities or internal states with the belief that great leaders are made, not born.

Application

According to this theory, people can learn to become leaders through teaching and observation. Behavior theories examine whether the leader is task oriented, people oriented, or both. Studies conducted at the University of Michigan and Ohio State University in 1945, established two major forms of leader behavior namely: employee-centered and production-centered (Hersey and Blanchard, 1988).

Trait theories of leadership explain the leadership traits that have been studied to determine what makes certain people great leaders. The practical application of the theory is looking at how the leader's

behavior affects their subjects. The trait approach is very different from the other leadership approaches as it concentrates on the leader and not on the situation or the followers or other circumstances or factors. This approach emphasizes that having a leader with a certain set of traits is critical for a leader to be effective.

Empirical Review

Akram, Alam, Ali, & Mughal, (2012) conducted a research title How Leadership Behaviours Affect Organizational Performance in Pakistan. Sample size used by the researchers is 1000, where 500 questionnaires were distributed to managers and another 500 to employees of various private and public sector companies in 66 cities through random selection. Non-probability sampling technique is used in this study. Two questionnaires were designed for managers and employees. Questions were related to leadership behaviours and organizational performance. Five point Likert scale was applied. Correlation analysis and regression analysis were applied to analyse the relationship and the effect of leadership behaviours on performance. SPSS version 16 was used to analyse the reliability of questions, and the reliability was checked in term of Cronbach's Alpha. The findings concluded that leadership behaviours are interrelated and have high positive impact with employee performance.

Dalluay & Jalagat (2016) conducted a research on title Impacts of Leadership Style effectiveness of Managers and Department Heads to Employees' job Satisfaction and Performance on Selected Small-Scale Businesses in Cavite, Philippines. The sample size used is 150. Survey questionnaires were designed to study the effects of manager leadership styles on employees' performance and satisfaction. 150 respondents were selected from corporations in Cavite, Philippines through random sampling with Slovin formula with $n = N/(1+Ne^2)$. Data were analysed by using weighted mean, percentages, multiple regression and correlation coefficient. Percentages specifically were used to analyse demographic variables (gender, age, length of service and leadership styles). Weighted mean were used to survey questionnaires on leadership styles, and correlation coefficient and multiple regression were used to study the relationship between variables on leadership style, job performance and job satisfaction. The finding concluded that corporations should constantly making the most of leadership style which enhances employees performance and employee job satisfactory level even though there is still rooms for improvements.

Gimuguni, Nandutu, & Magolo,. (2014). concluded that there is a moderate high positive and significant relationship between the three leadership styles (autocratic, laissez-faire, democratic), and performance in Mbale local government. The researchers revealed further findings that Mbale local government leaders use autocratic style of leadership to influence employees to perform their duties, but laissez-fair style of leadership dominated Mbale local leadership which could have caused delay in meeting deadlines. The findings also revealed that the local government has realized some performance in terms of increased work forces, high speed of accomplishment of work, effectiveness and timeliness due to democratic leadership. It was therefore concluded that Mbale local government tries to integrate the three leadership styles though autocratic and laissez faire dominated.

Ipas (2012) did a study on the perceived leadership style and employee performance in hotel industry, they found that autocratic leadership style is perceived as being the most used style by the managers that ensures expected results. They also stressed the fact that managers must find the good solution to help the employees to increase their individual performance.

Ismail, Tiong, Ajis,. & Dollah, (2011) worked on a research titled Interaction between Leaders and Followers as an Antecedent of Job Performance: An Empirical Study in Malaysia. Sample size used by the researchers is 200. This study used a cross-sectional method to integrate the research literature, the in-depth interview, pilot study and the actual survey to collect data. Convenience sampling technique was used. SPSS version 16 is used to analyse validity and reliability of data. Pearson correlation analysis and descriptive statistic is used to access research variables. Standardized coefficient of Stepwise regression

analysis was used. The findings confirmed that interaction between leaders and followers does act as full antecedent of job performance.

Kehinde and Banjo (2014) also did a test of the impact of leadership styles on employee performance: A study of department of Petroleum Resources; The implication of their study was that “transformational leadership style” would bring effective results in organizations because it motivates employees to go beyond ordinary expectations, appeals to follower’s higher order needs and moral values, generates the passion and commitment of followers for the mission and values of the organization, instills pride and faith in followers, communicates personal respect, stimulates subordinates intellectually, facilitates creative thinking and inspires followers to willingly accept challenging goals and a mission or vision of the future mission and objectives of organization, they recommend that transformational leadership style is good or appropriate for organizations that wish to compete successfully and mentor subordinates who will be managers of tomorrow to keep the flag flying for the firm. “Leadership has got a paramount attention in both the academia and practitioners since recent decades as determinant factor on employee behavior and performance”.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used survey research design. The researcher also utilized the survey strategy for this study because it creates room for gathering large amounts of data from a sizeable population in a cost-effective way

Population of Study

The National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) is a mandatory, post-tertiary scheme set up by the Nigerian government during the military regime of Head of State, Yakubu Gowon, to "reconstruct, reconcile and rebuild the country after the Nigerian Civil war". There is no military conscription in Nigeria, but since 1973, graduates of universities and polytechnics have been required to take part in the National Youth Service Corps program for one year. The population of study is made up of all the staff of the NYSC, Onitsha. The total number of workers in the employment of the NYSC, Anambra chapter as of this date is 173. Hence, they formed the population of this study. The population will serve as the sample size because they are not up to 1000 population.

Sources of Data

The primary source of data was the sampling or study unit regarding in (or form) which information is collected on first hand basis. The researcher did not adopt any rigid method in the collection of data; rather data was collected as the problem demanded creativity and judgment also played a vital role at this stage of the project, knowing that the final judgment will be partly constrained by the type and value of the information collected.

Method of Data Collection

The major instrument used in this research work is the questionnaire. Questionnaire was drafted and scrutinized by the supervisor which was subsequently distributed to the respondents to elicit important information concerning this research work. The questionnaire was open-ended in nature and was structured in such a way that the respondents will have a clear understanding of the questions.

Method of Data Analysis

Statistics such as frequency count and percentages were uses in the analysis of research questions while research hypotheses were tested using ANOVA. The research hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Analysis will be carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Introduction

This chapter dealt with the information collected in the field, as questionnaire was used to support some deductions. The observed data were presented in a frequency distribution table with percentages.

However, out of the one seventy-three (173) copies of the distributed questionnaire, One hundred and thirty five (135) copies were found relevant for the study, Therefore, the presentation and interpretation was based on the one hundred and thirty five (135) relevant copies.

Bio-data Analysis of Respondents

4.2.1 SEX

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid MALE	102	74.5	75.6	75.6
FEMALE	33	24.1	24.4	100.0
Total	135	98.5	100.0	

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2025

The above table reveals that the one hundred and two (102) of the respondents which represents 75.6% were male respondents, while thirty-three (33) respondents which represent 24.4% were female respondents. By implication, male respondents were more than female respondents by 51.2% in our selected population sample for this study. The implication of this is to enable us to know the number of female and male that successfully returned their questionnaire.

4.2.2 AGE BRACKET

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid BELOW 25 YRS	46	33.6	34.1	34.1
26-35	45	32.8	33.3	67.4
36-40	34	24.8	25.2	92.6
41-ABOVE	10	7.3	7.4	100.0
Total	135	98.5	100.0	

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2025

The table above shows that respondents whose age bracket falls below 25yrs were forty-six (46) which represent 34.1 percent. This is followed by those with age bracket of 26-35years with forty-five (45) which represents 33.3%. Also those within age bracket of 36-40yrs were thirty-four (34) which represents 25.2%. This is followed by those with age bracket of 41-above years with ten (10) which represents 7.4%. The implication of this age distribution is to enable us to check if the questionnaire was directed to the right age group.

4.2.3 MARITAL STATUS

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid SINGLE	105	76.6	77.8	77.8
MARRIED	28	20.4	20.7	98.5
OTHERS	2	1.5	1.5	100.0
Total	135	98.5	100.0	

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2025

In the table above, out of the one hundred and forty-eight (148) respondents, one hundred and five (105) of the respondents were single. While twenty-eight (28) respondents which represent 20.7 percent are married. Two respondents (2) which represent 1.5 answered others. It is therefore glaring that the majority of the respondents were single as at the time of this study. Thus marital status table help us to know the number of single, married, and divorce respondents that answered the distributed questionnaire.

4.2.4 EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid GCE/WASCE	23	16.8	17.0	17.0
OND	45	32.8	33.3	50.4
BSC/HND/BA	55	40.1	40.7	91.1
MSC/MBA	12	8.8	8.9	100.0
Total	135	98.5	100.0	

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2025

The table above indicates that twenty-three (23) respondents which representing 17% maintain to acquire have acquired GCE/WASCE, while 33.3% of the respondents which represents forty-five (45) ordinary national diplomas. However fifty-five (55) which represent 40.7 percent either have BSC/HND/BA. The respondents that have MS.C/MBA are numbered 12 which represent 8.9%. This is the one of demographic item helps us to identify the education qualification of the respondent.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One

H01: Authoritarian style of leadership has no significant effect on organizational service delivery

ANOVA

Table 4.3.1

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	139.809	2	34.952	47.346	.000
Within Groups	90.065	133	.738		
Total	229.874	135			

Sources: SPSS Output 2025

In testing this hypothesis, the F-statistics and probability value in table 4.7 is used. Authoritarian style variables have a F-statistics of 47.346 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Authoritarian style of leadership has significant effect on organizational service delivery

Hypothesis Two

H0₂: Laissez a faire style of leadership has no significant effect on organizational service delivery

ANOVA

Table 4.3.2

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	182.143	2	45.536	40.358	.000
Within Groups	137.652	133	1.128		
Total	319.795	135			

Sources: SPSS Output 2025

Second hypothesis has f-statistics of 40.358 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses and conclude that Consultative style of leadership has significant effect on organizational service delivery

Hypothesis Three

H0₃: Democratic style of leadership has no significant effect on organizational service delivery

ANOVA

Table 4.3.3

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.746	2	.373	7.286	.002
Within Groups	161.869	133	1.305		
Total	162.614	135			

Sources: SPSS Output 2025

The test conducted revealed that the large significance value (F.sig<.002) indicate no group differences. Since the F-value of 7.286 with a significance of .002 is less than .05 (i.e .002<.05), there exist no group difference. Democratic style of leadership has no significant effect on organizational service delivery.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

The leadership function fulfills the role of procuring employees and creating the necessary atmosphere or environment for them to perform managerial function, success is achieved through good leadership style and quality leaders are the priority of any business organization, the reason attributed to this, the direct use of resources to achieve desired objectives.

- From the study carried out, it was discovered that leadership style has a positive and significant relationship with organizational service delivery. The researcher also noticed that the nature of job and the philosophy managers have, affects their style of leadership.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made as regards the study carried out.

- ❖ Leaders of business organization should adopt participative style of leadership to ensure success and growth of their business.
- ❖ Leaders should instill in their subordinates a sense of ownership, direction and belongingness to the organization.
- ❖ Leaders should be honest, patriotic, intelligent brave and above all dedicated to their duties

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